

Deliverable 3.5
Specification of new
pilot funding calls

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 741527 and runs from May 2017 to April 2021.

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Project Acronym	ORION	
Project Title	Open Responsible research and Innovation to further Outstanding Knowledge	
Grant Agreement no.	741527	
Start date of the project	01/05/2017	
End date of the project	30/04/2021	
Work Package number	WP3 – Open Experiments	
Deliverable Number	D3.5	
Deliverable title	Specification of new pilot funding calls	
Lead Beneficiary	ISCIII	
Due date	M24 (April 2019)	
Date of delivery	04/06/2019	
Nature	R (Report)	
Dissemination level	PU (Public)	
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Version	Contributors	Comments
1.0	ISCIII	ISCIII first draft
2.0	JCMM	Content from Brno call
3.0	BI, CRG	Revision and comments

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Executive summary

The aim of sub-task 3.2.1 is to develop new and revised approaches to research funding. The two research funding organizations in ORION, the *Instituto de Salud Carlos III*, ISCIII (Spain) and the South Moravian Center for International Mobility, JCMM (Czech Republic) worked together and took complementary approaches to explore integration of RRI principles in funding processes, co-creating funding calls with multiple stakeholders, thus ‘opening-up’ the research funding engine. . ISCIII designed the RRI awards in health to reward those institutions that implant the RRI dimensions in their Institutions, and JCMM designed and ran a student competition on Open Science projects for the Brno universities.

ISCIII organized co-creation experiments that gave the opportunity to take into account different points of view from Stakeholders in different areas in order to work together on institutional changes. As a result, the call text for the RRI Health Prize has been amended in the Grant Agreement of ORION, to better reflect the objective of this prize: to recognise, encourage, promote and disseminate best practice examples on RRI aspects developed in 2019 by the Health Research Institutes. These Institutes accredited by the ISCIII will assure the excellence of the proposals to be submitted and constitute the leverage of more than 162 institutions, 24,000 researchers and 31 Health Research Institutes for all over the Spanish regions. The official pre-announcement of the call will be in May 2019. Three prizes of 10.000 € each will be awarded in 2020, for efforts on RRI from these Health Research Institutes in the course of 2019.

JCMM aimed to provide support to students with a chance to become more professional in Open Science. Two meetings were held in June and October 2018, during which they defined the domains of the local societal challenges. The eligible applicants were master and PhD students. The call was open for two months, followed by two-step review. In the first stage, they had set up a public peer review on the Authorea platform, but the participation by the public was poor. In the second stage, they organized an expert review with two experts per project. They received 45 eligible applications from three universities. In mid-April the 10 winners have been announced. These students have now 9 months to finalize their projects. JCMM has used an IT JCMM system to ensure the smooth processing of all applications as well as the evaluation management. This sophisticated tool is used in JCMM for registration of all applicants, evaluators, tutors, supervisors, administrators and JCMM personnel. The novelty of the evaluation procedure is part of the co-creation procedure. The experiences that JCMM learned will be used in other activities focused on students and in designing new calls with OS elements.

Instituto de Salud Carlos III, ISCIII (Madrid – Spain)

The Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII) is the leading Public Research Institution which funds, administers, and performs biomedical research in Spain. It is administratively dependent from the Spanish Ministry of Innovation and Universities (MICIU) and functionally dually dependent from the MICIU and the Spanish Ministry of Health, Consumption and Social Welfare. In addition to its research activities, ISCIII is a national reference centre for specialized techniques servicing the Spanish National Health System that carries out teaching and training activities through the National School of Public Health; funds research projects and research networks on health sciences through the Fund for Research in Health Sciences (*Fondo de Investigaciones Sanitarias*, FIS); and houses the National Library of Health Sciences. ISCIII is involved in basic and advanced training of health professionals to cope with the society health care demands.

Background on the preparation of the RRI Prize on Health

The new Pilot Funding Call is being developed under the framework of co-creation experiments to open up the research engine. The ISCIII, aware of the importance of generating changes in the Funding Organizations, selected one of the main structures that belong to the National Health System (NHS) for developing this new funding call. The chosen organisations were the Health Research Institutes (*Institutos de Investigación Sanitaria*, IIS).

The Spanish National Law [14/2017](#), 3rd July, on Biomedical Research establishes the parameters for every collaboration between the NHS and any other institutions or organizations involved in research concerning the joint use of scientific infrastructures and the research projects development. According to the ISCIII Statutes (**art.3.5 of RD 375/2001**, of 6 April), the ISCIII, as a scientific and technical health accreditation body, is responsible for the accreditation of those units and centres that reach the level of public health and research services determined by regulation.

[Royal Decree 339/2014](#), 27th February, on the IIS accreditation process, regulated the procedure for the accreditation of research institutes (currently repealed).

[Royal Decree 279/2016](#), 24th June, on the IISs accreditation process pursues, based on the development of Art. 88 of Law 14/2017 on biomedical research and within the framework of current administrative powers, to update the regulation of the accreditation and re-accreditation process. This royal decree is issued under article 149.1. 15th and 16th of the Spanish Constitution which grants the State exclusive competence in the promotion and general coordination of scientific and technical research and in the area of bases and general coordination of health.

The Health Research Institutes¹ (IIS) configuration was therefore proposed as it was determined to be the most suitable for the project proposed.

IISs General Objectives are:

1. To promote the Hospitals association with other centres in order to build multidisciplinary research Institutes.

¹The Health Research Institutes (*Institutos de Investigación Sanitaria*, IIS) are entities dedicate to basic and applied research related through the association of hospitals of the National Health System, universities, public research organisation (including primary health services) and other public or private research centres, with the aim of constituting multidisciplinary research institutes. The accreditation process developed by ISCIII is a recognition of excellence of scientific results and the beneficial returns resulting from research work in the hospital environment.

2. To scientifically contribute to substantiate the NHS programs and policies, promoting translational research.

IISs Specific Objectives are to:

- Promote the raising of public and private funding
- Define a common governance and strategy model.
- Establish a new organizational alliances model.
- Ensure an efficient infrastructure and resources use.
- Prioritize strategical research lines in health and clinical interesting areas.
- Strengthen alliances with other research groups.
- Encourage collaboration and cooperation with other research groups and networks.
- Promote excellence in biomedical research.
- Increase the critical mass of basic scientists and multidisciplinary clinicians.
- Increase basic and clinical research.
- Promote and encourage the dissemination and use of the results of basic and clinical research.
- Promote the professional training of all the personnel assigned to the Institutes.

On 12th April 2019 the new guide for accreditation (evaluation) was published, and the re-accreditation procedure with Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) indicators has been established through these dimensions:

1. **Government**
2. **Scientific Strategy, capabilities and performance**
3. **Impact**

RRI implies new thresholds and scientific-technical requirements; and the incorporation of subjects concerning diversity and gender equality, conflicts of interest, transparency, open access, open science and the modernisation of the research evaluation to be efficient in the implementation of RRI.

There are currently **31 IISs** distributed throughout Spain: Cataluña (7), Madrid (7), Andalucía (5), Valencia (2), País Vasco (2), Galicia (2), Castilla y León (1), Murcia (1), Cantabria (1), Aragón (1), Navarra (1) and Islas Baleares (1).

The IISs have gradually incorporated into the infrastructure:

- In **2009**: 6 IISs – Cataluña (4), Andalucía (1) and Valencia (1).
- In **2010**: 4 IISs – Galicia (1) and Madrid (3).
- In **2011**: 6 IISs – Cataluña (1), Madrid (2), Valencia (1), Andalucía (2) and País Vasco (1).
- In **2012**: 2 IISs – Madrid (2).
- In **2014**: 3 IISs – Castilla y León (1) and Cataluña (2).
- In **2015**: 8 IISs – País Vasco (1), Andalucía (2), Murcia (1), Cantabria (1), Galicia (1), Aragón (1) and Andalucía (1).
- In **2019**: 2 IISs – Navarra (1) and Islas Baleares (1).

Nowadays, the 31 IISs leverage more than 162 instructions and 24,000 researchers.

Organized Events

1 - National Stakeholder Workshop on Open Science (Madrid, ISCIII. 14th Nov 2018)

Considering that the participation of different stakeholders is critical for the success of the ORION project, four National Stakeholder Workshop were held in Prague, Bonn, Cambridge and Madrid.

In Madrid, the event was coordinated by the CRG and the ISCIII. There were 32 participants from several Spanish regions. Stakeholders were selected from various representative areas (**Science communication, research management, policy makers, funding, education, innovation and patient representation**) to provide an individual and specialized feed-back.

The meeting was distributed in two sessions. During the first one, a keynote speech on Open Science was given by Professor Eva Méndez followed by a short presentation on ORION and key results from its preliminary surveys.

The second session was moderated by Mandarin de Newton and followed a world-café methodology. Participants rotated among three tables to discuss the following WP3 ORION Activities:

1. A Prize on RRI in Health Research
2. Public Dialogue on research strategy at CRG
3. Citizen Science and the co-creation of a science video-game at the CRG

Focussed on a Prize on RRI in Health Research, the following questions were asked:

- What is RRI for you?
- What do you think is essential for an RRI project to win a prize?
- What is the right timeline for the prize in your opinion?
- How would you measure the criteria for a winning RRI project?

The main outcomes were the following:

In order to create a new Prize on RRI, it is important to take in consideration 4 main concepts:

- RRI is based on three key pillars: **people** (democracy, under-represented groups and openness of science to citizens), **economy** and **ethics** (values and sustainability). The prize must incorporate these three aspects.
- It is important to decide whom is the prize for. A good option would be to find exemplary RRI projects aligned with their institution. In this way, **the project and institution would be awarded**. It is seen as a better option to award several prizes of smaller amount than a single one for a very high value.
- The main objective of this award seems to be **to encourage more and better RRI projects**, so, a single call for punctual awards is perceived as something poor. There are two proposed options to overcome the punctual aspect of a prize: to transform the prize into a recurrent call or to ensure the continuity of the award over time.
- As an evaluation method, the use of **rubrics** is proposed. Three important aspects are valued: participation, the inclusion of under-represented groups (for example women) and scientific novelty, following European evaluation criteria.

2- ORION Co-creation “To Design RRI Health Prize” (Madrid, ISCIII. 28th Jan 2019)

From November 2018 to January, 2019 meetings were held at ISCIII to organize the co-creation workshop and discuss some of the following subjects:

- Selection of the IISs as a target group.
- Schedule and procedure to launch the RRI Health prize (right):
- Different stakeholders were selected to attend the co-creation workshop, in order to get feedback from different profiles (Principal investigator, financial manager, scientific directors, communication staff, PhD student and senior researcher).

Pre-announcement	May 2019
Submission	January 2020
1 st Phase Evaluation	February 2020
2 nd Phase Evaluation	March 2020
Prize award	April/May 2020

On the 28th of January 2018, a co-creation workshop was organized to define the criteria and sub-criteria for the evaluation of a Prize on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) within the ORION context.

Our workshop had the following structure:

1. Welcome, introduction and warm up exercises.
2. Activities for creating groups trying to make them as diverse as possible.
3. Implementation of RRI at the IIS: find strengths and weaknesses.
4. Brainwriting exercise on the sub-criteria: this activity was designed to establish the evaluation sub-criteria thinking on the three-evaluation axis: excellence, impact and implementation.
5. Priority dartboard to get consensus on the best criteria and sub-criteria.
6. Assessment of the RRI aspects.

From the data analysis we concluded that the Prize should give credit to:

- Some program or strategy focus on funding.
- Some agile strategies or working methodologies that imply less bureaucracy and better timing.
- A real transformation in relation to gender issues.
- Transparency of the project and/or the institution.
- Improving research processes holistically.
- Internal training.
- A closer relationship with society.

If we distribute these items along the European evaluation axes: excellence, impact and implementation, we get the following classification:

Implementation	Excellence	Impact
Some program or strategy focus on funding.	If we improve the research methods, we will get excellent holistic results.	A closer relationship with society.
Some agile strategies or working methodologies that imply less bureaucracy and better timing.		
A real transformation in relation to gender issues.		
Transparency of the project and/or the institution.		
Internal training.		

Participants find implementation the harder aspect of RRI, therefore we believe that it would be good to take this into consideration and have a close look at candidates for implementation.

This is the result of the Brainwalking exercise after asking participants about their proposals on how to choose the sub- criteria on how to evaluate the excellence, the impact and the implementation. It is important to measure:

- The level of internationalization and collaboration with other entities.
- The economic solvency of the projects and research groups.
- Publication impact.
- Working teams transformation, especially for gender issues.
- The involvement and bonds with patients.
- Having some RRI evaluation criteria established.
- Introducing new structures (reliable open data bases) and new methodologies.

If we compare results from this and the earlier activity, we find 9 strategic key points to do the evaluation:

Some program or strategy focus on funding.	The economic solvency of the projects and research groups.
Some agile strategies or at least some working methodologies that imply less bureaucracy and better timing.	Introducing new methodologies.
A real transformation in relation to gender issues.	Working teams transformation, especially for gender issues.
Transparency of the project and/or the institution.	Introducing new structures (reliable open data bases).
Improving research processes holistically.	Publication impact.
A more close relation with society.	The involvement and bonds with patients.
Internal training.	
	The level of internationalization and collaboration with other entities.
	Having some RRI evaluation criteria established.

Conclusions

As conclusions of this second workshop, we propose that the criteria and sub-criteria of evaluation of the RRI projects candidates to win the prize organized by ISCIII should take into consideration the following 10 key strategic points:

1. The economic solvency of the projects and research groups.
2. Some agile strategies or working methodologies that imply less bureaucracy and better timing.

3. Working teams transformation, especially for gender issues.
4. Transparency of the project and/or the institution, through new reliable open database structures.
5. Improving research processes holistically and the publications that come from these research projects.
6. Science transfer to society through Science dissemination and real problem solutions.
7. A closer relationship with society and patients.
8. The level of internationalization and collaboration with other entities.
9. RRI training inside the scientific community, as well as training for general audiences.
10. Having some RRI evaluation criteria established for the institution and for the project.

The two workshops greatly contributed to the new focus of the RRI Health Prize. As an outcome, in April 2019 the call text for this RRI Health Prize has been adapted by an Amendment of the ORION Grant Agreement, to better reflect the objective of this prize: **to recognise, encourage, promote and disseminate best practice examples on RRI aspects developed in 2019 by the Health Research Institutes**. In addition, these events also served to raise awareness of this call. The second workshop was attended by participants from 24 IIS. The official pre-announcement of the call will be in May 2019. Three prizes of 10.000 € each will be awarded in 2020, for efforts on RRI from these IIS in the course of 2019.

South Moravian Centre for International Mobility, JCMM, (Brno-Czech Republic)

Description

JCMM – South Moravian Centre for International Mobility was established in 2005 to support talented students and researchers in the region. The initially developed activity has been split into several specialized programs focused on these groups: college students, PhD students and post-docs. An additional scheme was established for supporting foreign college students (e.g. from Russia, Kazakhstan, Armenia, Serbia) to first learn Czech languages in their home countries; and after mastering the Czech basics, for applying for studies in Brno/South Moravia. Activities promoting the scientific principles and scientific work understanding (e.g. “T-excursions” – a day in a laboratory) gave impetus to join the ORION consortium and further promote the Open Science principles.

Outcomes

Events organized/participated in:

- The basic format of the call was first debated at the Smart City Brno Committee meeting on June 21st, 2018, where the idea was presented and feedback was sought from the participants. This committee was comprised of stakeholder representatives, including the local government, the Brno City Municipality, local universities, private companies and the local people engaged in the generation of a funding call addressing local societal challenges – it was suggested that the call would be divided into six research domains that would cover the areas of interest while fitting the profiles of public college students in Brno.

From July to September the JCMM staff worked on the call and promotion materials, namely the Guide for Applicants.

- The other important meeting took place on 4th October 2018 with the assistance of representatives from the “Ambassadors for Brno Eco-system”, which is the local equivalent of the quadruple helix approach. During the meeting the *guide for applicants* document was fine-tuned and it was defined how the call would be administered, how RRI principles could be integrated and which call domains were to be confirmed. These domains comprise specific areas:
 - Life science
 - Environment
 - Social
 - Economics
 - Technology
 - Medicine

Time-line of the call

Period	Description	Organization/individual involved
4/10/2018	Brno Ambassadors Round table / panel attended by JMK, MMB, universities, JCMM, public, CEITEC, student representatives; to define "local societal challenges" topics that students will address in their projects	JCMM City of Brno Academia Quadruple Helix
15/11/2018	Call Announcement (open for period o2 months)	JCMM
15/1/2019	Deadline of the Call	JCMM
16 – 31/1/2019	Eligibility check	JCMM
1 – 28/2/2019	Public peer review – <i>Authorea</i> web page	Public
1 – 31/3/2019	Evaluation of the submitted projects by external evaluators	Evaluators
15/04/2019	Announcement of the winners of the competition	JCMM
05/2019 – 01/2020	Individual projects carried out by students	Applicants

- A workshop within WP3 was organized by JCMM on November 29th, 2018. The event was hosted by the Brno Urban Centre and attended by potential applicants from almost all eligible Brno universities. The workshop objectives were to acquaint interested students with the ORION program and its application procedures as well as the open science principles which are still quite new for future researchers.
- The call was also announced on the [ORION website](#) and Twitter account.

A guest speaker was invited to join the event - Mr. Jiří Marek, manager of Smart City Brno projects. Mr. Marek is one of the leading experts on open science in the Czech Republic as well as an active member of the Smart City Brno Committee which has initiated a big number of citizen led activities. He gave an overview of OS principles and its importance for H2020 and Horizon Europe projects.

Relevant documents produced for the call:

- A promotion leaflet (see Annex).
- The [Guide for Applicants](#) and the [application template](#) – this material gives a detailed overview of the requirements for applying to the competition.
- Guide for Evaluators – material that provides instructions on how to evaluate the proposals.

Managing the pool of Evaluators

JCMM has a vast pool of external evaluators with extensive experience of evaluation of EU projects, namely projects funded under FP 6, FP 7 and Horizon 2020. These experts are familiar with the activities of JCMM as they have already participated in the evaluation of programs as COFUND SOMOPRO 1, 2, and 3 and a PHD competition to support talented students “Brno PhD Program”.

IT JCMM system

To ensure the smooth processing of all applications as well as the evaluation management an IT JCMM system was used. This sophisticated tool is used in JCMM for registration of all applicants,

evaluators, tutors, supervisors, administrators and JCMM personnel. A section called “ORION 2018” was open for paperless acceptance of proposals, registration of evaluators, matching the proposals and evaluators and the evaluation itself – a specific feature enables scoring as well as providing feedback to applicants. (This IT tool was established with no financial contribution of ORION and no costs are charged for use of the system from the ORION budget).

Evaluation

A total of 62 evaluators registered for JCMM competition and submitted their CV. Upon matching the profiles of evaluators and students we selected 40 participating evaluators, who were assigned between 1 to 3 proposals. There were 2 evaluators reviewing each proposal. We strictly adhered to the principle of excluding individuals from the involved institutions (i.e. universities); hence out of 40 evaluators, 30 experts were from European states, 2 were overseas and 8 were Czech citizens from academia/industry. There were 11 females and 39 males evaluators.

A total of 45 eligible proposals were received. Despite the active promotion only students from 3 public universities (Masaryk University, Brno University of Technology and Mendel University) submitted proposals. On the other hand, as the MU and BUT are the biggest ones, we received a large number of high quality proposals. Masaryk University provides education mostly in life and social sciences, economics, law, pedagogy and sports while BUT is focused on more technical subjects, e.g. civil engineering, architecture, engineering, IT and technology. Mendel university trains students in agriculture, horticulture, animal breeding and regional development. There were 15 applicants from MU, 23 from BUT and 7 from Mendel University. The male-female proportion of applicants was 24:21.

The call was open from November 15th, 2018 to January 15th, 2019.

1. In the eligibility check phase, done in the second half of January 2019, JCMM verified the formal requirements: length, language, mandatory 3 parts in the application [CV-applicant; co-creation project; team and facilities].
2. In the public peer review (February 1st – February 28th 2019) all proposals, i.e. the anonymized parts of the co-creation project, were uploaded to the [Authorea platform](#), which enables public review of the texts. We have circulated the information to the applicants, their supervisors and the public through information on our web page.
3. During the expert review (March 1st – March 31st, 2019), the evaluators were requested to express no conflict of interest with the proposal and to select their preferences according to the keywords and the abstracts. Then projects were matched with evaluators. Each proposal was evaluated by 2 experts and experts were requested to finish by the end of May. Then, in April, a special system sub-window was open and experts could see the score and comments of the other evaluators. For 8 days they could – seeing the other evaluation – adjust their comments and scores.
4. The 10 top proposals were announced on April 15th, 2019 while the rest were put on a reserve list. The composition of the 10 winners has an interesting gender unbalance: 9 female versus 1 male researcher. They have now 9 months to finalize their projects, a final report is expected from them.

ORION COMPETITION

MICHAEL DOLEŽAL, PROJECT MANAGER

In the public section, description of projects that qualified to ORION competition organized by JCOMM, Brno, Czech Republic

Joined Jan 2019 · Czech Republic

0 Publications 0 Connections

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ORION COMPETITION Last updated 4 months ago

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ORION COMPETITION Last updated 4 months ago

Detection and Localization of Tumour in Soft Tissues by means of ...

ORION COMPETITION Last updated 4 months ago

Screenshot of the proposals for public peer-review on the Authorea platform.

Conclusions

During the preparation of the call we did not encounter any problems. We especially appreciated the help and advice from partners that we run other activities with during our daily operations (i.e. the City of Brno representatives, the South Moravian Region Authority officials, the Smart City Committee, members of academia, the South Moravian Innovation Center, etc).

As the idea of promoting Open Science among students is quite new (although some of them are already familiar with the OS principles) it generated quite an interest and we were requested to give details about the ORION program, its partners and the scope of the program.

The only item that needs further improvement and better communication is the public peer review. If repeated, it will need more promotion and more encouragement for the public to get involved and give comments. However, for the Czech community the problem was the language, as everything around ORION is communicated in English.

ISCI Appendix

ORION “National Stakeholder
Workshop” 14 noviembre 2018 -
14.30 h a 19.00 h

Instituto de Salud
Carlos III
Escuela Nacional de Medicina del Trabajo (Edif. 13). Aula primera planta
(derecha) Melchor Fernández Almagro, 3
28029 Madrid

ORION es un proyecto colaborativo cuyo objetivo es implementar principios y valores tales como ciencia abierta e investigación responsable en centros de investigación y agencias de financiación. El proyecto cuenta con nueve socios en seis países europeos y está financiado por el programa H2020 de la Comisión europea (<http://www.orion-openscience.eu/>, 2017-2021).

El objetivo de esta sesión de trabajo es presentar y debatir los resultados de dos encuestas realizadas en el marco del proyecto ORION sobre las percepciones de la ciencia abierta por el público general en los seis países involucrados (incluyendo España) y por el personal de investigación de los socios de ORION. También se debatirán iniciativas de co-creación que el Centro de Regulación Genómica y el Instituto Carlos III desarrollarán en el marco de ORION en favor de una ciencia más abierta, tanto a nivel de desarrollo como a nivel de financiación.

La sesión será interactiva para dar la posibilidad de expresar sus opiniones a todos los participantes. Se han invitado representantes de diferentes sectores: ciencia, política científica, pacientes, comunicación de la ciencia y agencias de financiación.

AGENDA

1ª parte - 1 h 40 min Sesión (14:30 – 16:10)

- Moderación: Michele Catanzaro
- Keynote “Open Science”: Eva Méndez, Universidad Carlos III 25 min + 5 min preguntas
- Breve presentación general sobre ORION: Michela Bertero, CRG 10 min
- 2 presentaciones:
 - Resultados Public Survey ORION 20 min + 10 min preguntas
 - Resultados Self-Assessment Internal survey ORION: Marina Jimenez, CRECIM 20 min + 10 min preguntas

Pausa - 20 min

2ª parte - 2 h 30 min Sesión (16:30 – 19:00)

- Moderación: La Mandarina de Newton
- 3 sesiones interactivas de brainstorming
 1. Ciencia ciudadana y ciencia básica (CRG, Elisabetta Broglio)
 2. Diálogo con múltiples actores sobre la estrategia de investigación (CRG, Marta Solís)
 3. Premios de Investigación e Innovación Responsable en Salud (ISCIII, Laura Mohedano)

Breve presentación (“pitch”) de las 3 mesas redondas y luego discusiones interactivas. Resumen final de las discusiones.

TEMAS DE LAS SESIONES INTERACTIVAS

1. Ciencia ciudadana y ciencia básica

En el marco del Proyecto europeo ORION se quiere analizar si la aproximación de la ciencia ciudadana es oportuna y efectiva para facilitar la apertura de los científicos y de los proyectos de investigación a la participación de ciudadanos no expertos. Para esto, se han seleccionados dos experimentos de ciencia ciudadana que se llevarán a cabo durante dos años, unos de estos en el CRG (Genigma).

GENIGMA es un proyecto de ciencia ciudadana para investigar cómo se organizan los cromosomas en el espacio. Más concretamente, plantea co-diseñar con los ciudadanos un videojuego para analizar la estructura 3D del ADN de las células cancerígenas. El videojuego será la herramienta para analizar de forma participada muchas secuencias de genoma y descifrar patrones y anomalías de diferentes tipos de cáncer. Para que dé resultados, necesita de una amplia participación de jugadores, que vayan aprendiendo con el tiempo y se hagan “expertos” para poder resolver combinaciones cada vez más complejas del “puzzle” genético.

A partir de una definición genérica del concepto de ciencia ciudadana y su vertiente más amplia, la que implica la participación de los ciudadanos no expertos en múltiples etapas del proceso de investigación, identificaremos maneras de implicar la sociedad en la fase de co-creación previa al diseño del juego: algunas preguntas científicas ya están claras, pero en esta fase inicial los investigadores pretenden detectar e integrar más preguntas relacionadas con el interés de la sociedad.

Uno de los experimentos que se plantean en el Proyecto europeo ORION para fomentar la Ciencia Abierta entre los investigadores y así abrir la ciencia al público es llevar a cabo un “Public Dialogue” con diferentes agentes de la sociedad.

2. Diálogo con múltiples actores sobre la estrategia de investigación

Este formato de “Public Engagement” pretende pasar de la unidireccionalidad al diálogo auténtico entre científicos y diferentes stakeholders que estén implicados en la ciencia, desde asociaciones de pacientes a público general. El experimento pretende consultar las opiniones y necesidades de los diferentes stakeholders sobre la estrategia de investigación del CRG para el período 2021-2026 (siguiendo el hilo argumental de la medicina genómica) para luego diseñarla teniendo en cuenta e incorporando en la medida de lo posible estas visiones. De esta manera, no solo se implica a los diferentes agentes de la sociedad y se les sensibiliza sobre la importancia de la ciencia básica, sino que también se crean dinámicas internas entre los investigadores para abrir la ciencia del CRG.

Está previsto realizar dos o tres sesiones/workshops para llevar a cabo el “Public Dialogue” con diferentes stakeholders durante el 2019.

3. Premios de Investigación e Innovación Responsable (RRI) en Salud

El proceso participativo para el diseño de este Premio de RRI en Salud pretende reunirnos, como “stakeholders” del ciclo de investigación que sois, con el objeto de recoger vuestras opiniones y poder ayudarnos en el diseño de la convocatoria de dicho premio.

¿Qué vamos a hacer?

Diseñar la convocatoria de un Premio en RRI en Salud (Responsible Research and Innovation, RRI)

Este Premio es parte de las actividades que el Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII), como agencia financiadora, desempeña en el Proyecto europeo ORION.

Objetivo del Premio: Reconocer, fomentar, promover y difundir ejemplos de buenas prácticas sobre aspectos de Investigación e Innovación Responsable en salud dentro de las estructuras financiadas por el Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII).

Premios en Investigación e Innovación Responsable en Salud

Premiar las iniciativas institucionales que puedan servir como ejemplo de buenas prácticas en RRI.

Cantidad total: Se dispone de un presupuesto total 30.000 €. Se propone entregar 3 premios de 10.000 €/cada uno.

**ORION “Diseño de Premios RRI en Salud”
28 enero 2019 – 10:30 a 14:30**

Instituto de Salud Carlos III
Escuela Nacional de Sanidad (Edif. 8).
Monforte de Lemos, 5
28029 Madrid

ORION es un proyecto colaborativo cuyo objetivo es implementar principios y valores tales como ciencia abierta e investigación responsable en centros de investigación y agencias de financiación. El proyecto cuenta con nueve socios en seis países europeos y está financiado por el programa H2020 de la Comisión europea (<http://www.orion-openscience.eu/>, 2017-2021).

Se trabajará para establecer los subcriterios de evaluación de los Premios RRI en Salud. El objetivo del premio es reconocer las iniciativas institucionales que sirvan de ejemplo de buenas prácticas en RRI.

AGENDA

- | | |
|---------------|--|
| 10:30 - 10:45 | Introducción |
| 10:45 - 11:00 | Actividad para hacer grupos, de forma que nos queden grupos mixtos |
| 11:00 - 12:00 | Implementación de RRI en los IIS: determinar fortalezas y debilidades |
| 12:00 - 12:15 | Pausa café |
| 12:15 - 12:45 | Establecer subcriterios de evaluación teniendo en cuenta los ejes de evaluación (excelencia, impacto e implementación) |
| 12:45 - 13:15 | Priorizar los subcriterios más relevantes |
| 13:15 - 13:45 | Consenso de los subcriterios más importantes |
| 13:45 - 14:15 | Valoración de los aspectos de RRI |
| 14:15 - 14:30 | Cierre, agradecimientos y despedida. |

JCMM Appendix

Are you interested in pursuing an individual research project? Are you able to deal with societal challenges? Is a local development an issue for you? Can you contribute with innovative ideas and solutions? Yes? Then, explore fields of Open Science with us. Apply for one of the ORION scholarships offered to partner institutions. Participate in our Co-Creation Experiments!

Call for proposals 10x €5000 grants

Eligible applicants: full time university students from MU, BUT, MENDELU, VFU, UD, JAMU (only students of master's and doctoral programmes are eligible to apply)

Scholarships: equivalent of 5000€ / 9 months; 10 scholarships will be awarded in total

Use of resources: the scholarships should be used towards research (notebook, printer, literature, SW, laboratory materials & equipment, consumables, research trips, computer time, etc.)

For more information and application:
http://www.jcmm.cz/projekt/orion_en webpage

(electronic applications will be accepted through our portal).

Registration will be open between November 15, 2018 and January 15, 2019.

Supported research domains:

1. life science domain
2. environmental domain
3. social domain
4. economic domain
5. technical domain
6. medical domain

Individual projects should serve, help and be applicable in the South Moravian Region and/or the City of Brno and carry out elements of Open Science. It is recommended that your proposal is in line with your topic of your master and doctoral thesis.

We look forward to working with you. Orion team.

ORION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 741527.

Guide for Applicants

2018 Competition Round

ORION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 741527.

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Introduction to ORION and Open Science

ORION (Open Responsible research and Innovation to further outstanding knowledge) is a project funded under the Science with and for Society (SwafS) work program within Horizon 2020. The objectives of the project are to trigger evidence-based, institutional, cultural and behavioral changes in Research Funding and Performing Organizations (RFPOs) targeting researchers, management staff and high-level leadership. The long-term vision of the project is to embed Open Science (OS) and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in RFPOs (RRI-principles include ethics, gender, governance, open access, public engagement and science education). One of the ways that the project seeks to implement its objectives is to design, execute and evaluate co-creation experiments with relevant stakeholders, including the general public. In order to efficiently design such activities and adapt them to local audiences, knowledge of the attitudes among the general public(s) is crucial. Citizens of the countries that take part in the project (Czech Republic, Germany, Italy, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom) will be involved in several activities planned in the project (e.g. public dialogue workshops and citizen science projects).

Dan Gezelter [2009] in his reflection of The Open Scientific Project defines four basic objectives of OS: 1. Transparency in experimental methodology, observation and data collection. 2. Public availability and reusability of scientific data. 3. Public accessibility and transparency of scientific communication. 4. Using web tools to enhance scientific cooperation. The study you are going to implement should carry these principles. More information about the concept of Open Science can be found here:

<https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/content/what-open-science-introduction> or

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm>.

here:

In general, co-creation in the context of the ORION project is meant as a management initiative or proactive strategy that brings different parties together in order to jointly produce a mutually valued outcome. Co-creation brings a blend of ideas from different groups which in turn creates new ideas that contribute to solving societal challenges.

The representatives of the City of Brno, the South Moravian Region, JCOMM, NGOs, academia, regional businesses and public formed a consortium to define local societal challenges/call conditions to be addressed in the co-creation projects elaborated by students.

The aim of this competition is to identify top 10 students and provide them with a 9-month support, an equivalent of € 5000 per person. The proposals have to fit one or more domains as described in chapter 2.2.

1. Basic

Information

1.1 Terms

For the purposes of this competition, the following terms mean:

- 1) **provider** is the ORION consortium which provides financial support for the competition
- 2) **administrator** is the South Moravian Centre for International Mobility which is one of the ORION partners and organizes the competition
- 3) **applicant** is a student enrolled in a full time master's or doctoral study program at a partner university who applies for the scholarship
- 4) **evaluators** are experts in relevant fields in academia as well as professionals from the private sector and/or administration who provides expertise to evaluate submitted applications
- 5) **beneficiary** is an applicant who, based on the competition results, is awarded the scholarship

1.2 Partner Universities

The partner universities are:

- a) **Brno University of Technology**
- b) **Masaryk University**
- c) **Mendel University in Brno**
- d) **University of Veterinary and Pharmaceutical Sciences Brno**
- e) **University of Defence**
- f) **Janáček Academy of Music and Performing Arts in Brno**

1.3 Eligible students

The competition aims to support graduate and doctoral students. The selection of beneficiaries is based on excellent academic track record, experience and extraordinary activities of the applicants related to the research and open science or related activities. The quality of the submitted co-creation project and the team and facilities are also taken into account.

1.4 Eligibility Criteria

The competition is open and its rules set no quota of applicants for partner universities, faculties or departments. Therefore, do not hesitate to register. Ranking in the list is determined by the date of the first initial registration in the program, no further changes in the application have any influence on the listing.

Eligibility Criteria:

- Be a full-time student at a partner university as given in 1.2.
- are enrolled either in master's or doctoral study programs along the whole duration of the project
- co-creation project falls in research domains and serves the benefit of the South Moravian Region / City of Brno

All applicants declare their compliance with the eligibility criteria before submitting the application. The declaration is part of an electronic form in the registration system. Only the selected beneficiaries document officially their compliance with the eligibility criteria before signing an agreement with the administrator. Compliance with the criteria can be documented by a study confirmation issued by a partner university.

All applicants must also grant the administrator their approval to process the data provided in the application and its transfer to the third parties in order to evaluate the application or to disseminate its outputs. The full name and academic degrees of the applicants and their supervisors, the co-creation project title and the training department can be made public.

If a beneficiary has a permanent residence in a country where double taxation agreement with the Czech Republic is not signed, the scholarship will be automatically taxed by 35% and the beneficiary will be granted only 65% of the announced amount.

Please note that stipends of the Brno Ph.D. Talent 2016-2018 competition are not eligible applicants!

1.5 Time Schedule

The following schedule is indicative and minor changes may occur.

Table 1: Time schedule of the Orion Competition

Activity	Time period	Date
Competition Announcement		15/11/2018
Registration of Applicants	15/11/2018-15/1/2019	15/1/2019
Formal Review of Applications (1st Round)	16/1/2019-31/1/2019	31/1/2019
Open Peer Review of Applications (2nd Round)	1/2/2019-28/2/2019	28/2/2019
Expert Review of Applications (3rd Round)	1/3/2019-31/3/2019	31/3/2019
Publication of Competition Results		15/4/2019
Signing the Grant Contracts	15/4/2019 onwards	

Note: JCMM reserves the right to adjust the timetable in case of technical, administrative, legal circumstances.

2. Application Form

The applicants, who meet the eligibility criteria, can apply for the competition by submitting an electronic application. The applications are submitted during the registration period (see Time Schedule above) via a registration system available at our web page: http://www.jcmm.cz/projekt/orion_en or <http://www.jcmm.cz/projekt/orion>

The applicants register, create a personal account, fill in the online form and upload a PDF file. By the end of the registration period all applicants must confirm their application by clicking on the “register to the project” icon.

The registration system is quite simple and provides guidance; therefore, this guide does not describe it in more details. The application will be during the review process also transferred to the 3rd party digital platform due to the Open Peer Review process listed above (more information about the Open Peer Review can be found at the section 3.2 of this guide)

The applicant is responsible for the accuracy and completeness of the information provided in the application. If the applicant does not provide all the mandatory information, the application is formally invalid and cannot be accepted for evaluation. If the applicant provides inaccurate or incomplete information, it will be reflected in a reduced score. Applications containing false or unsupported data will be rejected. If any part of the application exceeds the maximum length allowed, then the extra pages will not be taken into account during the evaluation.

Overview of the application and its mandatory parts:

- **Applicant's CV** (1-2 pages)
 - o name, surname, address, email/cell phone number
 - o discipline and the start date of master's / doctoral studies, name of your university
 - o education and qualification for solving the proposed project
 - o professional practice/practical experience, internships, solved scientific projects
 - o relevant results of scientific activities and academic awards
 - o other relevant information
- **Co-creation Project** (2-3 pages)
 - o motivation, objectives and original contribution
 - o impact on/benefits for the South Moravian Region and City of Brno
 - o theoretical framework, methods and techniques, basic references
 - o time schedule and key milestones
 - o use of co-creation principles (see <https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm>)
 - o relation between the co-creation project and the applicant's research activity

- **Team and Facilities** (1-2 pages)

- o Supervisor and expert consultants, their contribution to the project, their open science or related topics activities, their qualification for guiding the applicant, main research activities, selected results of scientific and pedagogical activities, awards and recognitions etc.
- o institution(s) where the project will be solved, including planned visits & interactions, the information about institutional approach towards opening science is welcomed here
- o other relevant information

All three parts of the application must follow the above structure and presented in a **single PDF**. The maximum size of the file is **10 MB**. The application should not be shorter than 4 pages, the maximum length is **7 pages of A4 paper size**. The application may begin with a start page, which contains the project title and the applicant's name and it is not counted in the page limit. The application must be uploaded into the registration system (file name has to be „surname_name_2018“).

A template is available on the Orion web page.

The document must have the following format: font Times New Roman (or similar) of size at least **11 points** (references and notes can be written in 10 pt. font); single spacing or higher; all margins at least 2 cm wide; the heading of each page must contain the applicant's name and the competition title "ORION Open Science Co-creation"; page number must be indicated at the footnote. Other text format and graphic layout depend on the needs and preferences of each applicant (tables, graphs, pictures, etc.).

2.1 Applicant's CV

The professional CV provides information on your education, qualification and achievements. Highlight the results of your previous studies, scientific and open science related activities, particularly those related to your discipline and the topic of your project. We also recommend mentioning student awards, language exams and other accomplishments.

The permitted length of the CV is **one to two pages**. Be brief and give only relevant and verifiable information. The evaluators may check the information and the administrator may require proof of the data given in the CV.

Mandatory content of the applicant's CV:

1) DISCIPLINE AND STUDIES

Provide your personal data, name of your training institution and your field of study, date of admission

2) EDUCATION AND QUALIFICATION FOR SOLVING THE PROJECT

Detail your education and qualification in logical sequence, so that it clearly explains your specific competencies and qualities. Emphasize those that will help you solve the proposed project. You can also provide a list of special courses you have attended.

3) PRACTICAL EXPERIENCE, INTERNSHIPS, SCIENTIFIC PROJECTS

Mention your experience with scientific and open science related projects that you have designed and solved yourself. You can also provide a list of scientific projects in which you have participated and explain how. Provide information on your practical experience and training including a brief job description. Give a list of your internships or participation in university and professional organizations. Mention also summer schools you have attended and indicate their focus.

4) RESULTS OF SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITIES AND ACADEMIC AWARDS

List the results of your scientific activities and academic awards during the course of your studies.

5) OTHER RELEVANT INFORMATION

Finally, you can mention the knowledge and skills you have acquired in your everyday activities, which are not necessarily evidenced by official certificates and diplomas. In other words, make the list of your skills, knowledge and qualification complete. Describe clearly your language, technical, computer, presentation and other skills and abilities acquired during your studies, through seminars or informal training courses and free-time activities.

2.2 Co-creation Project

Your co-creation project should be built around “local societal challenges” and should actively seek innovative solutions that serve the South Moravian Region and/or City of Brno. For the purpose of your application a set of research domains have been defined and your co-creation project has to fit in one (or more) of the domains:

1. life science domain
2. environmental domain
3. social domain
4. economic domain
5. technical domain
6. medical domain

Example of a choice of topics in an environmental domain:

- water management/protection of resources (e.g. Brno dam pollution)
- natural resources optimization
- combating air pollution
- removing local old ecological burdens

The co-creation project may have a length from **two to three pages** of A4 paper size, including all charts, diagrams and references. Your supervisor can help you with its elaboration; however, do not forget to highlight your own contribution and explain the share of your work. Write the text for an expert in your discipline who is not informed about your specific project. Don't forget to mention how the principles of Open Science can help or spoil the aims of the project. Write clearly, be informative and brief.

Mandatory content of the co-creation project description:

1) MOTIVATION, YOUR ROLE, OBJECTIVES AND ORIGINAL CONTRIBUTION

Give a short overview of the proposed project. Explain clearly your personal role in the project and your motivation to solve the identified problem, reveal the expected benefits. The introduction should describe clearly and concisely the objectives and original contribution. Avoid general statements.

Explain how you plan to approach the problem addressed in the co-creation project so that the evaluators clearly understand what you intend to achieve. Also explain why your co-creation project is important, up to date and why it should be carried out. The evaluators will want to understand the main idea of the project as well as its importance and innovativeness.

2) IMPACT ON THE SOUTH MORAVIAN REGION AND CITY OF BRNO

Provide description what is the impact of your co-creation project for the benefit of the South Moravian region and/or the City of Brno

3) THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK, METHODS AND TECHNIQUES, BASIC REFERENCES

In this part of the project, describe the project design. Demonstrate the viability and originality of the proposed approach and its professional level. Explain what techniques and methods you chose and why you prefer them. Describe briefly the current state of knowledge of the problem addressed in your co-creation project and mention the previous work on the topic (if any). Focus on key references to show that you are familiar with relevant literature and that you are able to manage the project in detail but refrain from excessive and redundant referencing.

4) TIME SCHEDULE AND KEY MILESTONES

The project should be divided into stages. Each stage should have its own target and the achievement of all stages should guarantee the accomplishment of the overall objective. Define the milestones and set them in a time frame so that you can monitor and evaluate the implementation of the co-creation project. The total length of the co-creation is 9 months.

5) USE OF OPEN SCIENCE PRINCIPLES

Make sure that co-creation creates sustainable value with end-users and other stakeholders. Seek and develop new solutions/techniques/services/products that improve the quality of life of individuals and communities in e.g. technology, social inclusion, health care, education, resource efficiency, environmental issue, local economy, labor market etc. Co-creation actively involves end-users and other relevant parties in a full development process, from the identification of a challenge to the implementation and tracking of possible solutions. Part of the project should be also devoted to communication with public and explaining the importance of your research (e.g. participation in a „science cafe“, etc.). The important part of this part is also to create your own and simple Data Management Plan (DMP) for your project. There is no need of any standardized way of doing DMP. You can find inspiration here: <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/> or here: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm.

6) RELATION BETWEEN THE PROJECT AND THE APPLICANT'S STUDIES AND/OR THESIS

The title and the content of the project do not have to match fully the name or topic of your current studies. However, the project should be related to your studies or expected theme of your thesis (either master's or doctoral). Explain shortly the link(s) between them.

2.3 Team and Facilities

An effective supervision over the applicant's project and training as well as high quality facilities guarantee that applicant will successfully manage the proposed project. The permitted length is **one to two pages** A4.

1) SUPERVISOR AND EXPERT CONSULTANTS

Give a list of expert consultants who will significantly contribute to the project and ensure its professional quality. Explain their specific contribution, their qualification and key results of their previous work and open science related activities (if relevant) as well as their experience in supervision and mentoring of students. It is not necessary to mention all the consultants or collaborators.

2) DEPARTMENT AND COOPERATING INSTITUTIONS

High quality facilities may be crucial for successful implementation of the project. Describe briefly the facilities available at your training institution necessary for the proposed project. If your training institution lacks some special equipment, consider collaboration with other academic institutions or private sector and describe its rationale and benefits. Provide a list of planned visits and related open science activities of your or cooperating institutions.

3) OTHER RELEVANT INFORMATION

Finally, it is possible to provide other relevant information that you want to emphasize and which cannot be mentioned in other parts of the application.

2.4 Preparing the Application

Here are some general hints you should follow while preparing your application. Dedicating enough time to designing your co-creation project and writing the application is key for achieving the best results in the competition. The evaluators focus on your detailed state-of-the art knowledge of the chosen problem. The evaluators will also examine whether your project addresses an important and current scientific problems within a domain of your choice. The project design and viability are also very important criteria.

Your application should give clear answers to the following questions:

- **What problem is addressed in the project?**
- **Why you are interested in this topic and what is your role in the project?**
- **How do you plan to solve the problem?**
- **What are the expected results of the project?**

Keep in mind that the evaluators decide whether your project is worthwhile and well-designed, whether you are able to carry it out and the proposed outcomes are realistic. The addressed problem must be important, but not overly ambitious. It is important to clearly and strictly distinguish what you intend to do yourself and what will be done by your collaborators.

All of the above will be judged only upon your application. The evaluators will only learn the facts you provide them in your application. Your goal is to "sell" your previous results and achievements and to highlight your exceptional qualities in comparison to other applicants. Therefore, pay extra attention to make your application clear and informative. Avoid inaccurate or misleading data. Remember that vague or incomprehensible information may be the cause for a reduced score.

Ask yourself whether each sentence is clear and really necessary for understanding the project. Let your colleague or friend, who is not familiar with the project, read your proposal. Ask whether he or she understands your proposal. Such informal criticism can be very helpful.

3. The Competition

The competition has 3 rounds:

1. Formal review of applications
2. Open Peer Review of applications
3. Expert review of applications

In the first competition round the applications are formally reviewed. In the second the application is submitted through an open peer review platform (the specific one will be defined after the deadline for submissions ends) to enable an open peer review process of your application. Be aware, this means that your application and all the details in the application will be openly available on the internet for everyone to read and give comments. In the third round the content of the applications is evaluated. The last part of the evaluation process is anonymous; the names of the evaluators are not public. The results of each round are announced via the registration system or webpage and the administrator notifies the applicants by e-mail.

3.1 Formal Review of Applications

In the first competition round, the administrator carries out a formal review of applications. Only the applications that meet all the formal criteria pass to the second round for an open peer review or directly to third round to expert review, if the opt-out mode described below in the round two is used by the applicant. Applications that do not meet the formal criteria are invalid and cannot be accepted for further evaluation. JCMC reserves the right to contact applicants for further clarification in during the formal review stage.

The application is checked against the following formal criteria:

- The application has been submitted via the registration system during the registration period by the set deadline
- The application provides all the mandatory information specified in the second chapter of this guide
- The application is complete and provides all the required information
- The application has the required form, layout, length and language

3.2 Open Peer Review of Applications

This round serves to gather more insight and observation by the community of your field of study for the final decision of the evaluators in the third round. In case your project contains some part that cannot be shared openly, you have the possibility to point out this issue to the administrator of this call prior to submission of your application. In such case you need to describe clearly the reasons why you cannot submit part or all the application to the open peer review. The final decision about your application is based on the experts' recommendations and closing your application or part of it for this round will not alter your final results, but we strongly recommend to use this opt-out mode only if there is some legal or business reason for it.

3.3 Expert Review of Applications

In the third round of evaluation the applications are reviewed remotely by expert evaluators. The administrator ensures that each application is reviewed by at least 2 evaluators in order to establish the ranking of applicants. The evaluators review all assigned applications independently by scoring and commenting key parts of the application (applicant, project, supervisor & facilities). The aim of the comments is to provide feedback to the applicants, which they may use to improve their projects regardless of their result in the competition.

Table 2: Evaluation Scale

	EXCELLENT (100-81p)	ABOVE AVERAGE (80-61 p)	AVERAGE (60-41 p)	BELOW AVERAGE (40-21 p)	POOR (20-0 p)
Applicant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + demonstrates excellent results, his or her level is unique compared to other applicants +shows great qualification and motivation for chosen studies, for reaching the project objectives and obtaining original and scientifically valuable results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +demonstrates very good results, which are above average compared to others +great motivation for successful studies and accomplishment of the project objectives, expectations of acquiring original and scientifically valuable results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +demonstrates average results +well motivated to complete the project +expected results may be a useful addition to the current knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +the information provided shows that results and experience of the applicant are below average +It can be assumed that the applicant is not sufficiently qualified and motivated to complete the project and obtain scientifically valuable results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +the information provided shows very poor results and experience of the applicant +It can be assumed that the applicant is not qualified and motivated to complete the project and obtain scientifically valuable results
Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +very well designed, based on an original idea, with clear objectives +in terms of originality, importance and proposed solutions, the project proves an extraordinary quality which well exceeds the common level +the results promise a significant original contribution to the scientific knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +very well designed, based on a new idea, with clear objectives + In terms of originality, importance of ideas and proposed solutions, the project's quality is above average +the results may be useful for further development of scientific knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +based on correct assumptions, contains interesting ideas, the proposed solution is viable, its quality is average compared to other projects +the project design is generally correct but not fully clear in details and requires additional work + the project objectives can be achieved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +original contribution of the project is unclear, expected results have minimal impact on the development of scientific knowledge +methodology is incomplete and the objectives cannot be achieved without additional adjustments +the design and the time schedule are not suitable for reaching the objectives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + the original contribution of the project is negligible or none +the project is just a variation of a known solution +the methodology does not allow the achievement of the objectives, the time schedule is inadequate, it is not based on correct assumptions
Team and Facilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +supervisor, external consultants and department facilities provide a supportive and inspiring environment +their experience and excellent results guarantee successful project implementation and applicant's training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +very good department facilities and reputable supervisor and external consultants with necessary experience and significant results +It can be considered as a guarantee for successful project implementation and applicant's training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +department facilities, supervisor and consultants are at average level +standard results and experience +the team and facilities are sufficient for successful project implementation and applicant's training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +the information provided shows that the department, supervisor and consultants are below the average, demonstrate minimum international experience and collaboration +the team and facilities do not provide a credible guarantee for successful project implementation and applicant's training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +the information available suggests that the results of the department, supervisor and consultants are very poor +negligible or no international experience +the team and facilities do not guarantee successful project implementation and applicant's training

Table 3: Score Calculation

Evaluated Area	Partial score	Weight	Total points
Applicant	0 – 100 points	30 %	0 – 30 points
Project	0 – 100 points	50 %	0 – 50 points
Team and Facilities	0 – 100 points	20 %	0 – 20 points
Total	–	100 %	max. 100 points

In the next phase, the second review is made available to the evaluator for revision of his or her scoring and comments. At this stage, the evaluators can correct their views having taken into account the opinion of the second evaluator. If, after the revision, any two reviews of the same application differ significantly, the application will be reviewed by a third evaluator.

When all the applications are reviewed, the administrator sets up the ranking of applicants after the third competition round. The ranking of applicants is determined by the overall score of their application. The overall score is a simple average of two expert reviews. If there are three reviews, the overall score of the application is the simple average of two reviews with closer score.

The final results of the competition will be announced on the JCMM website. There is no legal entitlement to grant a scholarship.

Conclusion

The beneficiaries will sign an agreement with the administrator. The agreement is expected to be signed shortly after the announcement of the final results. One of the prerequisites to conclude the agreement is to provide a confirmation of student status of applicant and, if requested by the administrator, other documents referred to in the application.

The scholarship in the total amount of € 5,000 (equivalent in CZK) will be paid to the beneficiary in three instalments, 40% as prefinancing, 30% as interim payment and 30% after the final presentation and delivering the co-creation project. However, the beneficiary must fulfil a series of commitments stated in the agreement; otherwise the financial contribution will be withdrawn. A brief project description will be annexed to the agreement.

There is a commitment to submit a brief monitoring report in the middle of the period to be given interim payment. Furthermore, the beneficiary agrees to continue in his / her university study without interruption and notify the administrator of any change in his / her student status, as well as of any substantial change in the co-creation project. The beneficiary also confirms that he or she will observe the rules of publicity and open science principles and will cooperate with the administrator.

Grant holders could be invited to a seminar that will acquaint them with principles of open science and responsible research and innovation.

Beneficiaries will present their co-creation project to a stakeholder panel at a closing event. The dates and arrangements will be announced in due course.

Supervisors of the grant holders will be remunerated for their involvement in the selected projects.

Contact

If you have any further questions regarding the competition, please, do not hesitate to contact us. Mr. Michael Doležal, ORION project manager; e-mail: michael.dolezal@jcmm.cz
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